

A Look at the Current Automated Capabilities of Traceability

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Abstract

The development of large scale, real-time military systems requires the tracing of requirements as mandated by DOD-STD-2167A. In order to comply with this requirement it is necessary to use an automated traceability tool. This paper examines the process and criteria for evaluating traceability tools for use with real-time system developments.

1 Background

A primary concern in the development of military systems is ensuring that the design of the system meets the specified requirements. As part of the systems development and maintenance, many designs and tradeoffs are made that affect the integrity of the overall process. To ensure that the system meets the current set of requirements, traceability of the requirements to the design is essential. For the purpose of this paper, the term traceability is defined as a process in which the requirements are related to the elements of the design (e.g., system requirements, functions, data, hardware, software, humanware, testing, etc.) [2].

Currently there is a lack of a clear cut methodology for mapping requirements and design. Current system/software military standards mandate the use of traceability throughout the specification process but do not mandate or suggest the manner in which this traceability is obtained and maintained. Two recent projects at the Naval Surface Warfare Center Dahlgren Division (NSWCDD) have established a need for an immediate solution to the traceability problem. The need for both a method and a supporting environment is imperative.

This paper outlines the steps taken in evaluating traceability tools and offers some general observations about the state of the technology. Since different organizations have different business needs, it is

inappropriate for this paper to allude to or recommend specific traceability tools. Therefore, no tools are mentioned; only criteria and overall observations are discussed.

2 Motivations

The need for a useable traceability tool prompted a study to evaluate the utility of a current commercial traceability tool that was available within NSWCDD. The study showed that the tool did not meet the immediate or long term needs of the projects. The investigation also uncovered a number of traceability issues that need to be addressed by the research community.

The lack of current support for traceability prompted a search for a tool that would fit the needs of the current project. The investigation was a follow-up to some earlier investigations which examined several different state-of-the-art traceability tools.

The lack of automated traceability support seems to be an industry wide problem and not unique to NSWCDD. This report shows some of the evaluation techniques used to fill the specific NSWCDD traceability needs as they apply to the broader engineering community.

3 Initial Criteria

There were several major factors which allowed us to eliminate many of the current traceability products. The tool had to fit into our current CASE environment. This included a strong interface with the structured analysis (SA) [1][3] and publishing products which the project currently used. Another important feature was that the tool must support a graphical interface. Any tool not supplying such an interface would be too clumsy and time consuming to use on a large project. The tool also had to run on the same workstation platform that

currently held the specifications. Therefore, none of the PC based traceability tools were considered.

4 Pre-study Investigation

In order to better evaluate traceability tools it was necessary to gain a clear understanding of the project's traceability needs. This proved more difficult than expected. It was unclear as to what would be needed from a traceability tool. Also, the project's goals changed mid-stream, affecting what was being asked for from a traceability tool. After several meetings it was determined that the tool had to provide documentation traceability, strong interface with the SA CASE tool and publishing package, and on-line navigational capabilities. The remaining criteria were developed from past experience.

5 Evaluation criteria

To better organize the information, the evaluation employs five main criteria areas: Process, Capture, Output, Administration and Miscellaneous.

5.1 Process criteria

One of the first criteria is to judge the traceability schema, which poses the following questions: Does it support tracing to all design objects throughout the design process? Does it produce horizontal as well as vertical traceability? Does it allow tracing between requirements documents? Does it allow for easy recognition of transitive relationships? These questions evaluate whether the tool is robust enough to fit the sponsors' tracing needs.

Besides the traceability schema, how the tool parses, groups and manipulates requirements is another process criteria. Does the tool utilize keywords and attributes? Does it allow for regeneration of source documents?

5.2 Capture criteria

The tools must provide a Human Computer Interface (HCI) which is easy and intuitive for the operator. Specific concerns include the following: Does the tool allow for cut and paste operations between windows and native operating systems? Are the windows large enough? Are the windows scrollable? Does the system allow direct selection versus scrolling through a long list?

Besides the HCI issue, there are methodological issues in capturing the requirements and traceability information. Does the tool provide a convenient method for selection of requirements or design objects? Is the capture a natural part of the specification/design process? Does the methodology account for changing requirements? Does

the tool provide enough on-screen information to allow traceability capture? These issues are important to limit the overhead required in using the tool.

5.3 Output criteria

Capturing requirements traceability information is worthless if there is not an efficient and effective way of utilizing it. Questions regarding on-line viewing and reporting are critical to the tool's evaluation. Does the tool allow for online investigation of the traceability and requirement information? Can the user customize reports? Will the tool generate a traceability matrix? What is the cost (time) in producing useful traceability documentation? Are the generated reports easy to read?

5.4 Administration criteria

In order to fully investigate the tool, it was necessary to evaluate the overall administration of the tool. It is important to determine the amount of overhead involved in installing and maintaining the tool. For instance, how well does the tool handle project configuration and configuration management? Does the tool control access based on different security levels? Can the information be conveniently backed up?

5.5 Miscellaneous criteria

Finally, there are remaining issues that are important to gain a complete understanding of the usefulness of the tool. Does the company offer adequate training and customer support? Is the tool mature and stable? Is there a solid customer base? Is there a good chance that the tool will grow in the near future? Does the tool performance vary with the size of the database?

6 Observations

Based on our investigation, this section presents some basic observations of the state-of-the-art traceability tools. These observations are based on tools that meet most of the initial criteria, but appear to apply to most of the traceability tools on the market.

All of the tools seem to use a large relational type database and only show links of requirements and design. There also seems to be limited or no information on the links.

6.1 Process

It is apparent that no set methodology has yet been adopted for traceability; most tools have a "create your own philosophy" approach and suggest initial consultations. Some tools severely limit the range of tracing allowed. It is apparent that most, if not all of the tools, do not support a natural method of creating traceability as the design progresses. The majority concentrate on the front end of the design process: requirements capture, structured analysis, and structured design. Also, most do not link with simulation tools, implementation, or testing, but have a generic object that can be used to hold this information. It is apparent that there is no definition of requirements being satisfied, although some tools do allow marking requirements or links as satisfied.

6.2 Capture

Methods and HCI vary from graphical to pure text. The HCI and associated issues prove to be a major factor in the use of a traceability tool. A clumsy HCI ultimately makes a traceability tool almost unusable.

Similarly, the method for parsing the requirements and linking was found to be important. Even with a good HCI, if the parsing method itself is too cumbersome, then the tool becomes unproductive.

6.3 Output

The tools vary in their ability to display and report the traceability information. Preformatted reports are found to be more useful than always having to create a report from scratch. It is also important to be able to customize the report as well.

Also the report generating interface varies greatly. Some require knowledge of a sophisticated language to generate reports while other tools provide a simpler interface. Some tools also allow for generation of tables. In most cases, the generated tables are easy and quicker to read than the reports.

7 Conclusions

There is a noticeable improvement in most traceability tools since the initial examination in 1991. These improvements come mostly from customer feedback, with some from research and marketing. There is also a marked improvement in the integration of traceability tools with CASE tools and publishing packages, although further improvements are still needed. A strong methodology is needed for traceability, perhaps

independent of the tool (in the way structured analysis and structured design are independent of CASE implementations). It is found that varying levels of management support toward using traceability tools is a strong factor, e.g., whether the money spent for the tools is seen as a good investment varies. Likewise, there is a strong need for the creators of requirements and design to perform the traceability, not necessarily the tool experts.

There are traceability issues which need to be examined by the research community to enhance traceability technology. An overall traceability method needs to be developed which is independent of tools. The method needs to address issues such as the analysis of the relationships between the requirements and design, as well as relationships between design elements. If linking is used, additional information needs to be developed to allow for more robust traceability analysis [2]. Additionally, techniques for linking to different design methodologies must be supplied. The degree of granularity for traceability to be effective needs to be examined. A well defined method for maintaining and updating traceability information must be provided. Finally, research must be done to effectively and naturally integrate traceability into the overall design process.

References

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